

Supplementary Document: Similarity-Based Clustering for Root Cause Discovery in Clinical Knowledge Graphs

Information

This document contains supporting supplements for the academic paper titled "Similarity-Based Clustering for Root Cause Discovery in Clinical Knowledge Graphs". It is intended to accompany and aid the readers with figures, tables, and listings not presented in the source article. Whenever a "Supplement {X}" is referred to, it can be found here alongside a standalone caption and additional descriptions.

Supplements start on the next page.

Supplement 1

Our classification of common EHR errors under systemic and user-based factors. Examples from the literature are also provided.

Cause	Source	Description	Example
Systemic Errors	Inter-operability	Inconsistencies arising from integrating data across different EHR vendors or system implementations.	A lab test for "Creatinine" may be coded differently across two hospital systems, preventing aggregation [1].
Systemic Errors	UI/UX Design	Poorly designed interfaces that obscure information, increase cognitive load, or lead to misinterpretation.	Clinically relevant data that is hidden behind multiple clicks or in cluttered displays, is often overlooked [2].
User Errors	Data Entry	Mistakes made by users during the data entry.	Selecting the wrong diagnosis from a long drop-down menu; typographical errors in free-text fields [3].
User Errors	Note Bloat	The propagation of incorrect or outdated information through functions like copy-and-paste.	A resolved condition from a previous visit is copied forward into a new note, appearing as an active problem [4].
User Errors	Workflow Mismatch	Errors resulting from a disconnect between the intended clinical workflow and the EHR's supported process.	A clinician enters vital notes in a "special instructions" field that is not visible to lab technicians [5].

Supplement 2

SHACL shape categories, split by dimension and tier. Descriptions are provided.

Tier	Dimension	Category	Description
Ontology-Derived	Completeness	Missing essential variable	Identifies missing data elements.
Ontology-Derived	Consistency	Wrong datatype for property	Ensures values conform to expected data types.
Domain-Specific	Consistency	Time sequence	Identifies implausible event sequences.
Domain-Specific	Consistency	Invalid diagnosis for gender	Detects incompatible diagnosis–gender pairs.
Domain-Specific	Consistency	Invalid diagnosis for age	Detects incompatible diagnosis–age pairs.
Domain-Specific	Consistency	Invalid procedure for gender	Detects incompatible procedure–gender pairs.
Domain-Specific	Consistency	Invalid procedure for age	Detects incompatible procedure–age pairs.

```

@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<http://example.org/splitted_shapes#AIDAVAPatient_minCount_12> a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:closed false ;
  sh:ignoredProperties ( rdf:type ) ;
  sh:property [ sh:message "category:Missing essential variable",
                "dimension:Completeness",
                "id::aidava-shacl#b1b1db3cfb9f2dbb50e320d7f9ed745a",
                "message:The Patient needs to have at least 1 Administrative Gender" ;
                sh:minCount 1 ;
                sh:path <https://biomedit.ch/rdf/sphn-ontology/AIDAVA/hasAdministrativeGender> ;
                sh:class <https://biomedit.ch/rdf/sphn-ontology/sphn#AdministrativeGender> ] ;
  sh:targetClass <https://biomedit.ch/rdf/sphn-ontology/AIDAVA/Patient> .

```

The image shows a SHACL shape definition with several annotations:

- Unique Rule ID:** A callout pointing to the URI `<http://example.org/splitted_shapes#AIDAVAPatient_minCount_12>`.
- Descriptive Messages:** A callout pointing to the `sh:message` property within the `sh:property` array.
- Cardinality Constraint:** A callout pointing to the `sh:minCount 1` property.
- Target:** A callout pointing to the `sh:targetClass` property.

Supplement 3: An annotated SHACL shape. This rule states that all patients in the graph must have at least one gender associated with them. Can be used with another cardinality constraint, `sh:maxCount 1`, to dictate a patient must have exactly one gender.

Supplement 4: The diagram shows how SHACL Engines validate RDF graphs in this thesis. Dotted line represents a call made to an external process, the engine in this case.

```

@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .

<http://example.org/24fafd3ae42d03f42a3b9c56d4211c51fd900e161a1046c59a2f406831fee1ee>
  a sh:ValidationResult ;
  sh:resultSeverity sh:Violation ;
  sh:resultMessage "category:Invalid diagnosis for gender" ;
  sh:resultMessage "The subject $this, has code 1830 and M gender" ;
  sh:resultMessage "dimension:Consistency" ;
  sh:resultMessage "id:347223bb" ;
  sh:sourceShape <https://aidava.eu/shapes/Gender_Dx_1830-M-1> ;
  sh:sourceConstraintComponent sh:SPARQLConstraintComponent ;
  sh:focusNode <https://rdf.aidava.eu/resource/Admission/110613/Diagnosis/8.0> .

```

Supplement 5: An annotated validation result. This violation states the target patient has male gender and a diagnosis with code 183.0 (Malignant neoplasm of ovary), a medical discrepancy. Observe that this violation does not have a `sh:resultPath` associated with it. It is purposefully excluded as the violation could be caused by either a mistake in patient’s gender or the diagnosis code. See Figure 6 for an example.

Supplement 6: Two different types of noise injected to the same error-free graph. Notice that changing a patient's gender has more impact, i.e. triggers more violations, compared to when a diagnosis is changed.

Supplement 7: A standard Genetic Algorithm process, applied to the sequence optimization problem. Includes population initialization, parent selection, crossover, and mutation.

Parameters

I	: set of candidate VIOs, indexed by i
$T = \{1, \dots, n\}$: set of sequence positions
V_0	: initial number of violations in the KG
$r_i^-(V)$: violations removed if VIO i is applied at KG state V
$r_i^+(V)$: violations added if VIO i is applied at KG state V

Decision Variables

$x_{i,t} \in \{0, 1\}$: 1 if VIO i is applied at position t , 0 otherwise
$V_t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$: number of violations after step t

Model

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && V_n - V_0 \\ & \text{s.t.} && \sum_{i \in I} x_{i,t} = 1 \quad \forall t \in T \quad (1) \\ & && V_t = V_{t-1} + \left(\sum_{i \in I} r_i^+(V_{t-1})x_{i,t} - \sum_{i \in I} r_i^-(V_{t-1})x_{i,t} \right) \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2) \\ & && x_{i,t} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I, t \in T \quad (3) \\ & && V_t \geq 0 \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Supplement 8: MINLP Formulation for Most-Influential VIO Sequence Selection

Supplement 9: This extensive pictogram shows the fitness calculation for a VIO sequence. Each VIO is applied in the order of sequence and modifications are shown on a toy graph. Note that #4 and #8 are not visualized as they apply no change.

```

METHOD GeneticAlgorithm():
  P ← initialize_population(S, n) # initial population
  R ← [ evaluate_fitness(seq) FOR seq IN P ] # fitness values  $r_i$ 
  best_seq, ag-1 ← sequence with highest fitness, fitness score

  FOR g ∈ {1, ..., G} DO
    parents ← top_k_sequences(P, R, k = S/2)
    P' ← [best_seq] IF elitism IS TRUE ELSE []

    WHILE length(P') < S DO
      p1, p2 ← random_sample(parents, 2)
      child ← crossover(p1, p2,  $\gamma$ )
      child ← mutate(child,  $\sigma$ )
      append(P', child)
    END WHILE

    P ← P'
    R ← [ evaluate_fitness(seq) FOR seq IN P ]
    gen_best_seq, ag ← sequence with highest fitness, fitness score

     $\sigma$  ← adjust_mutation_rate(...)
    IF ag > ag-1 THEN # improvement
      best_seq, ag-1 ← gen_best_seq, ag
    END IF
  END FOR
  RETURN best_seq, ag-1,  $\sigma$ 

```

Supplement 10: Genetic Algorithm Pseudocode

Supplement 11

Changelog's Column Descriptions

Column	Description
Original Triple	The target triple before a VIO is applied.
New Triple	The target triple after a VIO is applied.
VIO Type	Short description of the applied VIO; explained by the MINLP formulation.
Added Violations	Hash id list of new errors that were triggered by this VIO.
Added Count	Number of newly triggered errors.
Removed Violations	Hash id list of errors that are no longer triggered after this VIO.
Removed Count	Number of errors that disappeared.

Supplement 12: High-Level Methodology

Supplement 13: An example PHKG, illustrating how data from different tables are integrated into a single, patient-centric graph. Data is from the publicly available MIMIC-III Demo.

- Comments**
- **Final:** 1 "Gender Change", 1 "Age Group Change", 1 "Admission-Discharge Swap", 2 "Delete Entity"
 - **Fitness (Net Violations):** 65

- "Code Change" never used.
- When simplified, the sequence reduces to 5 VIOs from 8.

#6 cancels #1

#4 applies no change

Supplement 14: The violation-maximizing VIO sequence output by GA after 20 generations. Simplification is carried out. Comments are included on the left to provide more insight to the result.

- (i) **Embedding = [Text, TransE, DistMult]**: Choice of embedding models for vectorizing violation subgraphs. Text embeddings use all-MiniLM-L6-v2^a from Sentence Transformers^b library, while TransE [6] and DistMult [7] are knowledge graph embedding (KGE) models from PyKeen^c library. TransE models a relation as a vector translation in embedding space, so that $subject + predicate \approx object$. DistMult uses dimension-wise scaling, scoring triples by the weighted dot product $\sum_i h_i r_i t_i$. In other words, TransE views a relation as shifting one entity vector to reach another, while DistMult views it as weighing how strongly two entity vectors align across their dimensions.
- (ii) **Kernel Type = [Gaussian, Cosine]**: Similarity function to be used for comparing vectorized subgraphs. The Gaussian measures how close two vectors (x, x') are by turning their distance into a score that decays smoothly from "identical" 1 to "far apart" 0 (see formula). Cosine similarity measures how close two vectors point in the same direction, regardless of their length (see formula).

$$\text{Gaussian}(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} \|x - x'\|^2 & \text{Euclidean Distance Sq.} \\ \sigma & \text{Kernel Bandwidth} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Cosine}(x, x') = \frac{x \cdot x'}{\|x\| \|x'\|} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} x \cdot x' & \text{Dot Product} \\ \|x\|, \|x'\| & \text{L2-norms} \end{cases}$$

We exclude Gaussian similarity from our experiment settings as a prior investigation showed that it reduces the performance drastically for any combination it is paired with. It is still kept as an option regardless.

- (iii) **Clustering Method = [Threshold, Hierarchical, DBSCAN, HDBSCAN]**: Choice of clustering algorithm to be used. Threshold clustering simply groups violations if their similarity exceeds a set value. Hierarchical clustering builds a tree of clusters by repeatedly merging the closest pairs [8]. DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) forms clusters based on dense regions of similar violations [9], while HDBSCAN (Hierarchical DBSCAN) extends this to find clusters of varying density [10]. These methods were chosen to cover a range of clustering strategies, from simple rule-based grouping to more flexible, data-driven approaches. Threshold clustering is excluded from the experiment as we can already pass it as a parameter to the other algorithms. Still, it is kept as an option and its process is detailed below.
- (iv) **Embedding Dimension = [256, 384]**: Controls the size of the vector used to represent each subgraph or entity in the knowledge graph. A higher embedding dimension allows the model to capture more detailed or complex patterns. Both options are large enough, moreover 384 is the default dimension for all-MiniLM-L6-v2 text embedding. Therefore, to reduce its dimension to 256, a separate autoencoder is built to function solely as a projection layer.
- (v) **Epochs = 10**: Loop length while training the embedding model. Kept at 10 to keep runtime reasonable. By our observations, this limitation did not affect the performance in a significant way.
- (vi) **Test Split = [0.1, 0.2, ..., 0.5]**: Sets what fraction of the data is reserved for testing rather than training or validation. Restricting it to this range ensures the test set is large enough for reliable evaluation but not so large that it leaves too little data for learning.
- (vii) **Threshold = [0.3, 0.4, ..., 0.9]**: Sets the minimum similarity required for two violations to be considered part of the same cluster. Adjusting this value controls how strict or relaxed the clustering is, with higher thresholds forming tighter, more exclusive groups.

^a<https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

^b<https://pypi.org/project/sentence-transformers/>

^c<https://pykeen.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

```

METHOD RootCauseClustering():
  noisy_CKG, SHACL_report ← Graph(...), Graph(...)
  ground_truth_clusters ← List[List[str]]
  G ← enrich_graph(noisy_CKG, SHACL_report) # merge graphs

  subgraphs ← []
  FOR v ∈ get_violation_ids(SHACL_report) DO
    f ← get_focus_node(v)
    g ← construct_subgraph(G, f) # 3-step neighborhood
    append(subgraphs, g)
  END FOR

  IF embedding == "text" THEN
    T ← [ serialize_to_text(g)  ∀g ∈ subgraphs ]
    E ← SentenceTransformer(T) # text embeddings
    A ← train_autoencoder(E, d) # reduce dimension to d
    Z ← A.encode(E) # projected vectors
  ELSE
    X ← collect_triples(subgraphs)
    E ← train_embedding_model(X, embedding, d) # KGes
    Z ← [ pool_embeddings(g, E)  ∀g ∈ subgraphs ]
  END IF

  S ← compute_cosine_similarity(Z) # similarity matrix
  normalize_similarity_matrix(S) # ensure S ∈ [0, 1], diag = 0

  C ← cluster(S, τ, method) # clustering with threshold τ
  C ← deduplicate_clusters(C) # remove duplicates

  M ← compute_metrics(C, ground_truth_clusters) # precision, recall, F1
  RETURN C, M, S

```

Supplement 16: Root Cause Clustering Pseudocode

References

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